

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 1 of 38

Title **Empowering Barangays: Harnessing Data for Effective Decision Making through Enterprise Resource Planning Systems**

Proponents **Adonis V. Garces, DIT**
Milagros S. Constantino, MIT
Reynaldo A. Valdez, Barangay Captain

Abstract

Barangays are the smallest administrative divisions in the Philippines, and they are crucial in local governance and community development. However, due to limited access to technological tools and data management systems, many barangays need help managing their resources, delivering public services, and making data-driven decisions. In response to these challenges, there is a growing recognition of the potential for Information and Communication Technology (ICT) solutions, particularly Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, to empower barangays and enhance their decision-making capabilities. This study explores the potential of ERP systems in improving decision-making at the barangay level by leveraging data effectively. ERP systems offer integrated solutions for managing various aspects of barangay operations, including finance, human resources, facilities and equipment, peace and order, and service delivery. By centralizing data and automating processes, ERP systems can streamline administrative tasks, improve transparency, and enable more informed decision-making among barangay officials. The data analytics module of the system enables real-time, interactive access, analysis, and visualization of resident profiles, senior citizen monitoring, collection and revenue monitoring, peace and order monitoring, the status of barangay facilities and equipment, and service delivery monitoring. The researcher will use developmental research to develop the system using Rapid Application Development (RAD) in agile project management. The study will be piloted in Barangay Ibung, Villaverde, Nueva Vizcaya. The overall system's compliance is evaluated using the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 25010 Software Quality Standards. Implementing ERP systems at the Barangay level can lead to more efficient resource management, better service delivery, and improved decision-making processes. These efforts can ultimately contribute to building sustainable, resilient, and inclusive communities, which are central to the objectives of SDG 11. By enhancing the decision-making capabilities of Barangays through data-driven approaches, the research can contribute to the advancement of sustainable development within urban and local contexts.

Keyword: ERP Systems, data-driven decision making, data analytics

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is a cornerstone of modern society, driving progress, innovation, and connectivity across various spheres of life. Its continued development and integration are essential for addressing global challenges and building a more inclusive and sustainable future (Smith, 2021).

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 2 of 38

A barangay is vital for grassroots governance and community development in the Philippines. The barangay, the lowest governmental body, is the primary implementer of development programs, initiatives, and policies (Carpio, 2020). Barangay plays a vital role in delivering essential services and addressing the needs of its communities. ICT has become a crucial part of people's everyday lives, and its integration into barangay operations is important because it is one of the supporting tools needed for barangay improvement. By harnessing the potential of ICT, barangay officials can better address the needs of their communities and promote sustainable development (National ICT Confederation of the Philippines, 2018).

Barangays' effective management and governance face numerous challenges, including limited resources, complex administrative processes, and disparate data management systems. In response to these challenges, there is a growing recognition of the potential for Information and Communication Technology (ICT) solutions, particularly Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, to empower barangays and enhance their governance capabilities.

An Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system is a software solution that integrates various business processes and functions across an organization into a unified system. The primary goal of an ERP system is to streamline and automate business processes, improve efficiency, and provide real-time visibility into various aspects of the organization. By consolidating data and processes into a single system, ERP software helps companies make better-informed decisions, optimize resource utilization, and enhance overall productivity. They can be deployed on-premises, hosted in the cloud, or provided as a hybrid solution combining both approaches.

Barangays, the smallest administrative division in the Philippines, could benefit from ERP systems in various ways: (a) ERP systems can help barangay officials manage resources more effectively, (b) ERP systems can streamline processes related to providing services to residents, such as issuing permits, managing public facilities, and responding to inquiries or complaints. It could improve the efficiency and transparency of barangay operations. (c) By collecting and analyzing data from various sources, ERP systems can provide insights that help barangay officials make informed decisions. It could include analyzing demographic trends, tracking service usage, or identifying areas for improvement. (d) ERP systems can assist barangays in complying with regulations and reporting requirements. They can automate generating reports for government agencies or auditors, reducing the administrative burden on barangay staff.

Barangay Ibung, in its early decade of operations, was very easy to perform and accomplish a task on time with traditional work approaches to paper piles. The scenario is very different from decades ago. Barangay Ibung has accumulated much data on residents, businesses, human resources, facilities and equipment, and peace and order. Barangay data management and decision-making have grown into an enterprise stage where barangay officials have to access data from different functional areas for planning, managing, and decision-making. This situation then requires a modern management tool rather than a traditional work approach. This can be done by adopting and integrating an ERP system into different functional areas.

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 3 of 38

Implementing ERP systems within barangay administration represents a transformative approach to data-driven governance, enabling streamlined operations, data-driven decision-making, and improved service delivery. ERP systems offer barangay officials comprehensive insights and real-time access to critical information by centralizing various administrative functions into a unified digital platform. It empowers them to make informed decisions, optimize resource allocation, and respond promptly to community needs. These efforts can ultimately contribute to building sustainable, resilient, and inclusive communities, which are central to the objectives of SDG 11. By enhancing the decision-making capabilities of Barangays through data-driven approaches, the research can contribute to the advancement of sustainable development within urban and local contexts

ICT in Governance

Mendoza (2018) emphasized that ICT improves governance through e-government programs. These programs seek to enhance service delivery, digitize administrative procedures, and advance accountability and openness in public administration. ICT tools have been crucial in easing barangay operations and promoting public participation. Examples of these tools include online portals, electronic document management systems, and digital communication platforms.

Alegre (2020) state that the idea of data-driven governance is to leverage analytics and data to guide decision-making. Barangay officials can assess the effectiveness of policies and programs, prioritize resource allocation, and obtain insights into community needs by utilizing ICT tools for data collecting, analysis, and visualization. Research has indicated that implementing data-driven strategies can improve the efficacy and efficiency of municipal governance.

Enterprise Resource Planning Systems

ERP systems integrate various business functions and processes into a single, centralized platform, providing real-time access to data and facilitating seamless coordination across departments. While ERP systems are commonly associated with private sector organizations, there is a growing trend towards their adoption in the public sector, including barangay governance (Gonzalez, 2019).

ERP systems are integrated information technology systems associated with operational application- subsystems (modules), which replace the separate autonomous software units developed previously to monitor core business processes such as accounting, sales, sales management, inventory and warehouse management, and manufacturing. Thus, the available business resources, as well as the organized and efficient handling of procedures, are performed in every modern enterprise in the best and most effective ways that users can fully utilize (Garefalakis, 2016). According to Kravchencko (2018), enterprise resource planning (ERP) is a computer-based system that unites various functions like inventory, accounting, inventory management, and human resources.

Data Management Systems

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 4 of 38

The Barangay management system was designed by Carpio (2020). It is an online system that allows locals to register, submit requests, and file complaints. The system facilitates the receipt and documentation of resident register requests, complaints, and document requests by the barangay secretary. Even on official business or away from the office, the barangay chairperson, as the authorizing authority, can approve requests, view and address complaints, and produce reports. Additionally, the system can notify locals via SMS about the status of their requests, complaints, or announcements about advisories and barangay ordinances.

Cerna (2023) created and implemented an office automation system to promote digital empowerment. The technology aims to automate the tedious barangay transaction processing process that is now in place. Its main goal is to make administrative tasks like document requests, complaint filing, and creating accurate and comprehensive reports easier.

Himo (2022) designed and developed a Community Request Queue Management System for the Local Government Unit of Cabanatuan City that gave the barangay hall and its officials a modern, convenient, and efficient way of performing their services. It lessened the population of people entering and leaving the barangay hall. It provided the Sumacab Sur Citizens with an alternative way of submitting inquiries, filing complaints, and requesting documents.

Cruz (2023) developed and evaluated a barangay management information system with a residency certificate issuance feature. This system yields substantial advantages for barangays in the realm of local e-governance. Optimizing administrative processes and simplifying document processing enhances operational efficiency within the context of digital governance initiatives. Furthermore, its pivotal role in establishing a comprehensive repository of essential records magnifies its potential to reshape local governance in the digital age.

Data Driven Decision Making

Elgendy (2022) elaborates on the DECAS theory and clarify the idea of examples of data-driven decisions. The paper proposes a modern data-driven decision theory, DECAS, which extends upon classical decision theory by proposing three central claims: (a) (Big) data and analytics (machine) should be considered separate elements, (b) Collaboration between the (human) decision maker and the analytics (machine) can result in collaborative rationality, extending beyond the classically defined bounded rationality, (c) Integrating the classical decision-making elements with data and analytics can lead to more informed and possibly better decisions.

Tacuban (2016) designed the Barangay Decision Support and Mapping System to address the needs of the barangay for efficient information and decision processing. It allows the record of all the barangay residents and enables the user to create and edit the map using the generally accepted symbols or icons. It automates the barangay clearances, and permits. It allows storing and retrieving barangay-approved ordinances, meetings, and resolutions. It records environmental problems and the solutions provided. The system also records cases of domestic violence, disputes, and the actions taken by the concerned officials. Moreover,

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 5 of 38

the system provides the necessary reports for barangay officials to use for their barangay planning activities.

Castro (2022) built a system that uses data mining techniques to generate insights and visualization to facilitate government organizations to oversee health and services to senior citizens. The system can aid in policy and decision-making and show areas that need immediate actions to deliver quality social services for senior citizen

ISO 25010 Software Quality Standards

ISO 25010 is a standard that defines a quality model for software product evaluation. It outlines characteristics and sub-characteristics that can be used to assess the quality of software systems. It provides a structured approach to evaluating software quality, enabling organizations to make informed decisions about software systems' suitability, reliability, and performance. The product quality model defined in ISO/IEC 25010 comprises the following eight quality characteristics: (a) Functional Suitability, (b) Performance Efficiency, (c) Compatability, (d) Usability, (e) Reliability, (f) Security, (g) Maintainability, and (h) Portability.

According to Frasca (2015), ISO 25010 is a standard for software quality; it presents a quality model that may be applied to any software product. ISO 25010 is currently the most complete version of quality models of ISO standards due to the many proposed quality attributes.

Conceptual Framework

Below presents the Input-Process-Output (IPO) model of the study.

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 6 of 38

Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

The study paradigm, as shown in Figure 1, follows the input-process-output diagram with a feedback mechanism. The study's input includes the existing practices, procedures, processes, and challenges of the barangay in data management and decision-making.

The other inputs include Barangay Premier, data sets, and ISO 25010:2015, which were used in the development of the system.

The process accepts the inputs, performs some operations, and transforms them into some state. The inputs are analyzed to develop an ERP System. The proposed system is developed to support barangay in managing their data and supporting their decision-making using RAD methodologies.

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 7 of 38

The proposed system is evaluated using ISO/IEC 25010:2015 Software Quality Standards. Likewise, further system improvements are determined and recommended. The feedback refers to the communication link that loops into the inputs, as these were the identified remarks gathered from the study participants to enhance the ERP system for the barangay.

Statement of the Problem

This study explored the development of an Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) System that supports barangay officials in their data management and decision-making. Generally, it focused on the development of ERP systems. Specifically, the study answered the following questions:

1. What are the current practices, processes, and challenges of managing data in the Barangay in terms of
 - a. Resident' demographic profile
 - b. Business permits and clearances
 - c. Peace and order
 - d. Equipment and Facilities
 - e. Human Resources
2. What are the problems encounter by the Barangay in their decision making process?
3. What system can be developed to support the barangay in their data management, and decision making?
4. What is the extent of compliance of the proposed system with ISO 25010:2015 Software Quality Standards as assessed by the user-participants and IT expert-participants in terms of the following:
 - 4.1 Functional Suitability,
 - 4.2 Performance Efficiency,
 - 4.3 Compatibility,
 - 4.4 Usability,
 - 4.5 Reliability,
 - 4.6 Security,
 - 4.7 Maintainability, and
 - 4.8 Portability?

Methodology

A. Design

The researchers used the descriptive and developmental study methods. Descriptive research is used to acquire data to answer questions. At the same time, developmental research refers to developing a system that addresses the respondents' problems or a specific population or organization.

The descriptive research design is used in the study to determine the existing practices, procedures, and issues in the Barangay's current processes in data management, decision-making and adopting the ERP system will end up having

competitive advantage that will improve planning and performance management and for better planning and control in operational efficiency and improve decision-making. Moreover, this is used to describe the data and characteristics of the system being evaluated using ISO 20510 Software Quality Standards for evaluation. This type of study design is an excellent method of data collection since it mainly provides answers to the questions that the researchers need for them to construct or develop the system.

The developmental research design is used in the study to create, evaluate, and develop an ERP system. The researchers utilized the Rapid Application Development (RAD). This methodology was divided into phases: (a) planning, (b) user design, (c) construction, and (d) cutover.

B. The Software Development

The development of the Barangay Enterprise Resource Planning System was organized based on the Rapid Application Development (RAD) process. The RAD was chosen because of its suitability to the project's scope, data, decisions, technical architecture, and requirements (Delima et al. 2017). The ERP development methodology used by Kokate (2014) was adopted in this study. Figure 2 illustrates the stages that will be undertaken following the RAD process.

Figure 2. *Rapid Application Development Stages*

The following are the phases of RAD that were undertaken:

- a. *Requirements Planning*. Requirements planning was carried out in the development of the Barangay ERP System. During this stage, the current situations are studied, the data are gathered, the system scope is defined, process redesign and workforce skills are also identified, workforce transition is determined, and the schedule is estimated. The researchers conducted interviews with the participants regarding the existing practices, processes, and challenges they encountered in terms of data management and decision-making. Likewise, the suggestions and recommendations of the participants on how to improve the existing practices and processes to solve the problems encountered are considered in this stage. The project scope are defined by identifying and describing how barangay officials, secretaries, and treasurers interact with the system, how data moves, and how transactions flow from one point to another. The involvement of the stakeholders at this stage were necessary. It was also important at this stage to determine what was out of scope, and this is properly documented.

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 9 of 38

At this stage, the scope and the functional requirements of the project are defined. This must not be changed without the appropriate change management functions that should take proper actions to address the shifting project requirements. To further avoid this scope creep, the researchers ensured that every user understood the requirements and agreed upon exactly how the project goals would be met.

- b. *User Design.* After careful identification of requirements, the user design stage is carried out. Clients and developers worked hand in hand to ensure that user needs were met at every step of the design process. Throughout the stage, the detailed activities and data associated with the Barangay ERP System are analyzed, and their interaction and integration with each component. The process flow of activities and data are streamlined by reducing steps and re-sequencing tasks most efficiently and effectively to perform tasks or activities correctly. The user must fully understand the process of redesign to use the system correctly and meet their expectations to support the development of the system.

The screen layouts are developed, and the construction approach is selected. Users tested each system prototype live on the client site at each stage to ensure it meets their expectations. The client tested the prototype and provided feedback on what worked and what did not in the iterative process until they reached a satisfactory design. This step was repeated as often as necessary as the project evolves.

- c. *Construction.* The system designs described in the User Design stage are implemented in this stage. Hence, the Barangay ERP System is developed and tested on the user site. During this stage, the fastest possible cycle of designing, coding, testing, modifying, and re-coding the system are done to produce an acceptable ERP System. The user gave input throughout the process. They suggested alterations, changes, or even new ideas that could solve problems as they arise. However, scope change must be managed effectively. This step will be repeated as necessary as new components are required or alterations are made to meet the project's needs.
- d. *Cutover.* In the Cutover phase, installation of the Barangay ERP system, user acceptance testing, and user training are performed. The system is deployed to a live production environment parallel to the manual operations process, where complete necessary testing took place with user training. This was the strategy to make users believe in the system. User from the start of the development may change their mindset as regards their new roles and responsibilities. Users and IT experts used the ISO 25010 Software Quality Standards evaluation questionnaire to evaluate the system.

C. System Architecture

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 10 of 38

Figure 3. System Architecture

The system architecture of Barangay ERP is a web-based client-server application that runs on a local area network. Functional areas, such as the barangay secretary or treasurer, are connected to the network with the centralized database, as shown in Figure 3. The Barangay Kagawad is also connected and can access the local area network to store data in the database, allowing other functional areas to retrieve and access information. The Data Analytics Module extracts data from the database, creating a model on the different functional areas, and serves as a guide in the decision-making process.

The Data Analytic Module used three models: behavioral, management science, and operation research. The behavioral model focused on studying and understanding the different behaviors/trends among the variables. A behavioral model is built by observing the previous behavior of an entity or a system; the resulting model can then be used to predict future behavior and performance using trend analysis and turnover rates. Management Science Model is based on the principles of management. It includes break-even analysis, supply reorder points, and aging accounts receivable. The operation research model is based on different mathematical formulae. It represents real-life problems depending on the various variables and the parameters expressed in the algebraic equations form. This model can be used in mathematical techniques such as collecting revenues (Abdirahman, n.d.).

Several users can use the system, including the Barangay Secretary, Barangay Treasurer, Barangay Kagawad, and Barangay Captain. The user can log in with a username and password but has limited access to the system based on the respective functional area. The system administrator can access all the transactions and reports, add/upload data, maintain data, and maintain system users by deleting, updating, and viewing users.

D. Locale

The researchers conducted the study at the Barangay Ibung in Villaverde, Nueva Vizcaya. Ibung is a barangay in the municipality of Villaverde, in the province of Nueva

Vizcaya. It was created by Batas Pambansa Blg. 889, known as "An Act creating Barangay Ibung South in the Municipality of Villaverde, province of Nueva Vizcaya into a new barangay to be known as Barangay Ibung South. Its population, as determined by the 2020 Census, was 4,416. It represented 21.95% of the total population of Villaverde. Ibung is situated at approximately 16.6068, 121.1858, on the island of Luzon. Elevation at these coordinates is estimated at 236.1 meters or 774.6 feet above mean sea level.

Figure 4. Research Locale

E. Participants and Sample

The main participants of the study were the barangay officials, barangay secretary, and treasurer, who are the users or beneficiaries of the proposed system. The IT experts were likewise selected as participants because of their valuable input, development, and system assessment.

The following were the participants of the study.

Table 1. Participants of the Study

Respondents	Population	Percentage (%)
Barangay Officials	8	62
Barangay Secretary	1	7
Barangay Treasurer	1	7
IT Experts	3	24
Total	13	100

The study involved eight (8 - 62%) barangay officials composed of the barangay captain, and the barangay kagawads as shown in Table 1. They were primarily involved in data management and decision-making.

There is one (1 – 7%) barangay secretary and one (1 – 7%) barangay treasurer. The study participants were selected using the purposive sampling technique, a non-probability sampling technique that relies on the researcher's judgment when choosing the units to be studied. IT expert participants (3 – 24%) were system developers and IT faculty.

F. Instrument

Interviews were conducted to gather relevant data on Barangay's current practices, processes, and challenges and address critical data management and decision-making issues.

Additionally, the researchers sought their consent to observe in their office to allow them to see the actual process or procedures based on their manual operations. In the observation process, the researchers took the key points of the challenges, struggles, or problems encountered in data management and decision-making processes. This aided in triangulating the data or information gathered from interviews and document analysis. The researchers followed the official office time for the observation.

Together with the interview and observation, the researchers asked permission to get other relevant data on their operations. The papers or data sets were used as the foundation for the system's activities.

ISO 25010:2015 Software Quality Standards was utilized to determine the quality of the proposed ERP system. The extent of compliance of the system to the standards is determined by the IT experts and users along the eight dimensions, namely: (1) Functional Suitability, (2) Performance Efficiency, (3) Compatibility, (4) Reliability, (5) Security, (6) Maintainability, (7) Portability, and (8) Usability.

G. Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers sought the approval of the Barangay Captain of Barangay Ibung, to obtain datasets. The researchers conducted interviews to determine the current practices, processes, and challenges related to data management, and decision-making.

This study underwent review by the SMU University Research Ethics Office (UREO) to ensure that all ethical standards and protocols are complied with.

H. Treatment of Data

The descriptive statistical tools used in the study were frequency, percentage, and mean. The weighted mean was used to determine the developed system's compliance with ISO 25010:2015 Software Quality Standards. The extent of compliance with the system was rated using the following Likert scale.

Table 2. Measurement of the Extent of Compliance with ISO 25010:2015 Software Quality Standards

Mean Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Compliant to the very great extent	The measure described in the item is compliant to the very great extent or OUTSTANDING .
3.40 – 4.19	Compliant to a great extent	The measure described in the item is compliant to a great extent or VERY SATISFACTORY .

2.60 – 3.39	Compliant to a moderate extent	The measure described in the item is compliant to a moderate extent or SATISFACTORY .
1.80 – 2.59	Compliant to a little extent	The measure described in the item is compliant to a little extent or FAIR .
1.00 – 1.79	Compliant to the very little extent	The measure described in the item is compliant to a very little extent or POOR .

I. Ethical Considerations

As stated by Gogoll et. Al. (2021), since ethical deliberation requires an innate willingness to invest time and resources, encouragement and support for the developers to consider ethical issues should be discussed and be prioritized. Consequently, ethically informed products promote success, and they help create better products in the future.

Concerning ethical issues, the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Office (SMU-REO) in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, is consulted before the study was conducted. This is situated in Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, the Philippines, at Rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, 2nd Floor, SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos (email: reb@smu.edu.ph; mobile: 09177053041).

This document certified that the primary purpose of this study is to develop an ERP system for the Barangay. The researchers provided oral and written explanations to the barangay officials about their right to refuse to participate, the boundaries of confidentiality of this study, and their right to have a copy of the survey results if they wish.

The respondents of this study were ensured to not be exploited for personal gain as the data collected from the respondents shall be securely kept with utmost confidentiality in mind. The data will remain with the researchers if the study and system are not finished or completed. Paper records are to be destroyed or disposed of in a manner that leaves no possibility for information reconstruction. For this, burning, shredding, and then cross-shredding shall be used.

The respondents of the study were protected from physical and mental harm and the researchers considered the preferences of each of the respondents to avoid future inconveniences during the conduct of the study.

Nothing from this study would have compromised the accuracy of the data and conclusions that the researchers obtained. Therefore, this paper does not contain any declared conflicts of interest.

J. Software Requirements

The computer programs used in developing the system for the web were PHP – Codeigniter and HTML for coding and enhancing the Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the system, MySQL (SqlYog v.10) for the database management, Notepad ++ was used in

writing the source code of the system. TeamViewer v.12 was used to modify the system off site online.

Table 3. Software Specifications (Web and Mobile)

Component	Specifications
Operating System	Windows 7 and above
Database Application	MySQL (SQLyog v.10)
Server	WampServer 3.0.6, Apache 2.4.23
Software Development	PHP – Codeigniter v3.1.3, HTML, App Inventor 2 NotePad++, TeamViewer v.12

K. Hardware Requirements

These were the recommended computer hardware, peripherals, and specifications for the implementation of the system. The barangay has the computer hardware in place which are functioning properly and in good condition both for the server and the client.

Table 4. Recommended Server Hardware Specifications

Component	Specifications
CPU	Intel Core i7
Memory	4GB
Hard Disk Space	1TB
Monitor	14” LCD
Keyboard	101/102 Keyboard
Mouse	Microsoft USB
Optical Device	DVD-R/RW
Printer	Epson 2100

Table 5. Recommended Client Hardware Specifications

Component	Specifications
CPU	Intel Core i3
Memory	4GB
Hard Disk Space	500GB
Monitor	14” LCD
Keyboard	101/102 Keyboard
Mouse	Microsoft USB
Printer	Epson 2100

Results and Discussion

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 15 of 38

Managing data in a Barangay involves various practices, processes, and challenges across different aspects, such as resident demographic profiles, business permits, peace and order, equipment and facilities, and human resources. Here's an overview:

A. Current practices, processes, and challenges of managing data

1. Resident's Demographic Profile

The management of residents' demographic profiles is still carried out manually using traditional paper-based records and logbooks. Residents submit their personal information through handwritten forms, which barangay officials then file and store in physical cabinets. Retrieving data requires manually searching through these documents, making the process slow and inefficient. Updating records is also labour-intensive, as it involves locating files, editing entries, and ensuring the accuracy of the information—often leading to human errors such as duplication or incorrect data. Generating reports poses another challenge, as officials must compile data manually for government submissions, making it difficult to monitor demographic trends over time. Furthermore, the security and preservation of physical records present significant risks, as documents are vulnerable to loss, damage, or unauthorized access. The absence of a digital system limits accessibility and delays data retrieval and analysis. Although some productivity tools are used for recording and storage, the overall manual process hampers efficiency, accuracy, and data security. This highlights the urgent need for a more structured and digitized approach to demographic information management in the barangay.

2. Business permits and clearances

The management of business permits and clearances is still carried out manually, relying on paper-based records and physical documentation. Business owners are required to submit written applications, which barangay officials review and record in logbooks or paper files. The approval process involves manually verifying submitted information, ensuring compliance with local regulations, and securing the necessary signatures from barangay authorities. Records are organized using traditional filing systems, making document retrieval time-consuming, particularly when officials need to verify or update a permit. Generating reports for business monitoring and renewal tracking also proves challenging, as officials must manually sift through records to identify expiring permits or compile summary reports. Moreover, there are security concerns due to the risk of document loss, damage, or misplacement, which can result in disputes or delays in processing. The manual system further increases the chances of human errors, such as duplication or incomplete information, thereby slowing down transactions. Although productivity tools like MS Word are used to print clearances and permits, the overall manual process remains inefficient, error-prone, and lacking in proper data security. These challenges emphasize the need for a digital system to streamline operations and enhance service delivery.

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 16 of 38

3. *Peace and Orders*

Peace and order data is handled manually, relying on written reports, logbooks, and physical records. Barangay officials document incidents, complaints, and blotter reports by recording details on paper, which are then stored in filing cabinets. The process of tracking cases, monitoring disputes, and updating resolutions requires manual searching and verification, making it time-consuming and inefficient. Coordination with law enforcement agencies, such as the police, also involves physical document submission, further delaying response times. Additionally, the manual system increases the risk of misplaced or lost records, which can hinder case follow-ups and weaken accountability. The lack of a centralized database also makes it difficult to analyze crime trends or generate timely reports for decision-making. Human errors, such as incomplete or inaccurate entries, further compromise the reliability of records. Overall, the manual process of managing peace and order data in Barangay Ibung limits efficiency, accuracy, and security, underscoring the need for a digital system to streamline documentation, improve case tracking, and enhance coordination with authorities.

4. *Equipment and Facilities*

Management of equipment and facilities is conducted manually, relying on handwritten records and logbooks to track barangay-owned assets. Barangay officials record the inventory, usage, and maintenance schedules of equipment and facilities on paper, storing these records in filing cabinets. The process of monitoring asset conditions, scheduling repairs, and tracking borrowed or rented equipment requires manual verification, making it time-consuming and prone to errors. Additionally, there is no centralized system for quickly retrieving information, leading to difficulties in ensuring proper maintenance and accountability. The risk of misplaced or outdated records further complicates asset management, making it challenging to track equipment availability and prevent unauthorized use. Report generation for budgeting and auditing also requires extensive manual effort, increasing the likelihood of inconsistencies in data. Overall, the manual system for managing equipment and facilities in Barangay Ibung is inefficient, prone to inaccuracies, and lacks proper security, highlighting the need for a digital solution to improve tracking, accountability, and maintenance management.

5. *Human Resources*

The management of human resources is conducted manually, relying on paper-based records and logbooks to track personnel information and other employment-related data. Barangay officials record employee details such as personal information, job roles, work schedules, and leave applications in physical files, which are stored in filing cabinets. Additionally, updating employee records, processing clearances, and tracking performance evaluations require extensive paperwork, making data retrieval and verification time-consuming. The manual system also poses security concerns, as physical records are vulnerable to loss, damage, or

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 17 of 38

unauthorized access. Overall, the lack of a digital system in managing human resources leads to inefficiencies, errors, and challenges in maintaining accurate and secure employee records, highlighting the need for an automated system to streamline processes and improve workforce management.

B. Problems encountered in their decision-making process

Barangay Ibung encounters several challenges in its decision-making process, primarily due to the reliance on manual data management and traditional governance methods. The absence of a centralized and digitized information system makes it difficult for officials to access accurate and up-to-date data, leading to delays and inefficiencies in making informed decisions. Generating reports on residents, business permits, peace and order, and resource management requires extensive manual effort, increasing the risk of errors and inconsistencies. Additionally, the lack of real-time data tracking hinders the barangay's ability to respond quickly to emergencies, resolve disputes, and allocate resources effectively. Communication gaps among barangay officials and the community also pose a challenge, as information dissemination relies on physical notices and word-of-mouth, which can lead to misunderstandings or delays in implementing policies. Furthermore, without a structured data analysis system, the barangay struggles to identify trends, assess community needs, and prioritize development projects efficiently. Overall, these challenges result in slow decision-making, reduced operational effectiveness, and difficulties in addressing the evolving needs of Barangay Ibung, highlighting the need for modernized processes and digital solutions to enhance governance and service delivery.

C. Developed System

Figure 5. Brgy ERP Main Module

Figure 5 shows the Main **Dashboard of the BrgyERP System**, which serves as a centralized management platform for barangay-level operations and services. The dashboard is designed with a user-friendly interface, providing administrative

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 18 of 38

access to different modules such as Dashboard, Residents, Place and Order, Blotter, Human Resources, Announcements, Utilities, and Settings.

The layout is simple yet functional. The sidebar navigation allows for easy access to critical modules needed for barangay governance and services, supporting activities like resident information management, report generation, human resource tasks, and local incident reporting. Additionally, it is designed to streamline administrative workflows and improve transparency, accountability, and efficiency in barangay-level governance.

1. Resident's Demographic Profile

Figure 6. Resident's Demographic Profile Module

The BrgyERP System, as depicted in the collage of interface screenshots, is a comprehensive and user-friendly Barangay Enterprise Resource Planning platform designed to streamline and digitize the management of resident data and reports. Its primary functionality revolves around the efficient handling of resident profiles, data analytics, and report generation. The **Residents**

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 19 of 38

Dashboard provides visual insights into demographic information, such as gender distribution, using intuitive charts that help local administrators make data-driven decisions. The **Manage Resident Profile** module allows users to maintain a centralized **Resident Master List**, where they can view, edit, and delete resident details including photo, full name, contact number, and gender. This supports up-to-date and accurate record-keeping essential for barangay operations.

Moreover, the **Manage Resident Reports** section enhances administrative capabilities by offering dynamic report generation tools. Through a dropdown menu, users can select specific types of reports such as the **Resident Master List**, **List of Indigent Residents**, **List of Senior Citizens**, **List by Occupation**, and **List by Income**, enabling targeted analysis and program implementation. The "Refresh" button suggests that the system retrieves real-time data, ensuring that reports reflect the most current information. The system also features an intuitive sidebar menu that provides quick navigation between major modules, promoting ease of use and operational efficiency. Overall, the BrgyERP System empowers barangay officials with essential tools for digital governance, resident profiling, and strategic planning, ultimately contributing to more responsive and transparent local administration.

2. Business Permits and Operations

Figure 7. Business Permit and Clearances Module

Figure 7 shows **Barangay Permit and Clearances Module**. The **Distribution of Collection Fees** dashboard presents a visual breakdown of financial collections,

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 20 of 38

including fees for clearances, certificates, and permits. This bar chart allows barangay officials to easily monitor and compare the volume of transactions by category, promoting transparency and informed budgeting decisions.

The **Manage Barangay Transactions** module features a searchable and filterable interface where officials can process various transactions for residents. Each row in the transaction table shows individual resident details—including name, gender, and photo—with accompanying buttons to process different types of requests such as Barangay Clearance, Certificate of Residency, Business Permit, and Indigency Certification. This setup allows for efficient and organized processing of barangay services while maintaining proper documentation and traceability for each transaction.

Furthermore, the **Manage Collection Reports** section offers a flexible reporting interface that lets users generate financial reports based on different sections and categories. Users can choose between reports such as the **List of Total Clearance Collections**, **List of Total Certificate Collections**, and **List of Total Business Permit Collections**, with a refresh button ensuring up-to-date data retrieval. This module enhances the financial oversight capabilities of the barangay, enabling officials to track income sources, assess service usage, and support fiscal accountability.

Overall, these functionalities illustrate that the BrgyERP System is a powerful and integrated platform that not only handles resident information but also supports essential barangay transactions and financial management processes. The system's modular design, real-time reporting, and interactive UI collectively improve the efficiency, transparency, and service delivery of barangay operations.

3. Peace and Order

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 21 of 38

Figure 8. Peace and Order Module

Figure 8 shows the Peace and Order Module of the BrgyERP (Barangay Enterprise Resource Planning) System is a vital component designed to support barangay officials in maintaining safety, order, and effective governance within the local community. This module offers a centralized and user-friendly dashboard that provides access to detailed reports and records related to blotters, crimes, and peace and order analytics. The dashboard prominently features a graphical representation titled "Distribution of Crimes," which visually highlights the frequency of various offenses within the barangay. This chart enables officials to easily identify the most common violations, such as breaches of local ordinances, and aids in the formulation of targeted enforcement and preventive strategies.

A core feature of the system is the "Manage Blotters" section, where barangay personnel can view and track blotter records including the date of filing, the names of the complaining party and respondent, the nature of the complaint, the location of the incident, and its current status. This organized view allows for efficient case monitoring and supports transparency in community-level conflict resolution. Complementing this is the "Manage Crimes" section, which records reported crime incidents in detail, capturing essential data such as the date reported, crime description, location, and case status. These features facilitate the proper documentation and follow-up of criminal activities, empowering barangay officials to respond more effectively to threats to public order.

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 22 of 38

Another key component is the "Peace and Order Reports" page, which includes a dropdown menu for generating various types of reports, such as the overall peace and order report, individual blotter and crime reports, and even crime graphical reports. These reports are crucial for administrative documentation, performance review, and submission to municipal or city-level agencies. The integration of data analytics and reporting in this module enhances evidence-based decision-making and fosters a culture of accountability.

The system also features a map view, which provides a geographical visualization of the barangay and potentially marks locations of reported incidents. This integration of spatial data allows barangay officials to better understand the distribution of incidents across the locality, improving patrol planning, resource allocation, and community engagement efforts. Overall, the Peace and Order Module of the BrgyERP System represents a significant advancement in local governance, leveraging technology to promote safety, organization, and responsive leadership at the grassroots level.

4. Equipment and Facilitates

Figure 9. Equipment and Facilitates Module

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 23 of 38

Figure 9 shows the **Facilities and Equipment Management** module of the BrgyERP System, showcasing its ability to monitor, manage, and report on barangay assets, supplies, and physical facilities. At the forefront is the **Facilities and Equipment Dashboard**, which visually presents the **School Supply ReOrder Level** through a bar chart. This chart offers a quick and effective way for barangay staff to identify which supplies are nearing depletion, thereby facilitating timely reordering and ensuring uninterrupted service delivery.

The **Manage Physical Facilities** section provides a detailed inventory list of barangay-owned structures and properties. Each record includes an asset code, description, classification (e.g., materials, tools), quantity, and unit value, along with actionable options for editing or deleting entries. This module ensures that the barangay maintains an up-to-date and organized log of its infrastructure and assets, aiding in planning, budgeting, and maintenance.

Alongside physical facilities, the **Manage Barangay Supplies** module deals with the consumable inventory such as office supplies. Supplies are categorized, coded, and listed with descriptions and quantities, enabling staff to track their usage and availability efficiently. This prevents shortages and promotes responsible inventory handling.

The **Facilities and Equipment Reports** section enhances administrative oversight through on-demand reporting features. Users can generate reports such as the **List of Supplies** and **List of Physical Facilities**, which offer summarized views of inventory data for accountability and auditing purposes. A dropdown menu paired with a refresh option suggests dynamic report generation based on real-time information.

Altogether, this part of the BrgyERP System plays a crucial role in ensuring that barangay assets, whether physical infrastructures or consumable supplies, are well-monitored, accurately documented, and efficiently reported. It contributes significantly to the systematic management of resources, supports transparency, and optimizes service delivery within the community.

5. Human Resources

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 24 of 38

Figure 10. Human Resources Module

Figure 10 shows the Human Resources Module, It presents a comprehensive overview of a Barangay Employee and Official Records Management System (BrgyERP Dashboard). This web-based application facilitates efficient record-keeping, monitoring, and reporting of barangay employees and officials. The dashboard interface is user-friendly and organized with a navigation panel on the left, providing access to different modules such as Home, Employees, Brgy Officials, and Reports.

Upon logging in, users are directed to the **Employee Dashboard**, which includes visual analytics such as a pie chart summarizing **employee gender distribution**, helping administrators to quickly assess gender representation in the workforce.

The **Manage Employee Profile** section displays a tabular list of employees, including fields such as Photo, Employee ID, RFID, Name, Gender, Mobile, Position, Status, and Action buttons (Edit/Delete). This section enables administrators to view and manage employee details, update profiles, and maintain data accuracy in real-time.

The **Manage Brgy Officials Profile** screen mirrors the employee management section but is specifically tailored for barangay officials. It includes official-specific identifiers and enables the tracking and updating of their roles and profiles.

Furthermore, the **Employee and Official Reports** section enhances the system's analytical capabilities by offering a dropdown selection of report types. Users can generate various reports such as: Employee Gender Count, Position Count, Total Employees per Unit, Barangay Officials List, and Gender Chart by Unit. This feature empowers decision-makers with critical data insights for planning, staffing, and policy development.

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 25 of 38

Overall, the system provides a centralized, efficient, and structured approach to managing barangay human resources and leadership profiles, with features supporting both data visualization and administrative control.

6. Business Intelligence or Data Analytics

Figure 11. Business Intelligence Module

Figure 11 shows the Business Intelligence Module that serves as a decision-support tool that transforms raw incident data into actionable intelligence. It promotes **informed governance**, reinforces transparency, and improves the barangay's capability to maintain peace and order effectively. It complements other modules in the system by integrating crime-related insights into the broader barangay management framework.

D. Extent of Compliance of the Developed System with ISO 25010:2015 Software Quality Standards

The developed Brgy ERP system was evaluated using the ISO 25010 Software Quality Standards as the instrument to measure the system's compliance with respect to functional suitability, efficiency, reliability, maintainability, portability, usability, security, and compatibility.

A. Extent of Compliance with ISO 25010:2015 in terms of Functional Suitability

Table 6. The System's Compliance on Functional Suitability as Assessed by the IT Experts and Users

Functionality Suitability	IT Experts		User		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Functional Completeness	4.42	Very Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.54	Very Great Extent
Functional Correctness	4.42	Very Great Extent	5.00	Very Great Extent	4.71	Very Great Extent
Functional appropriateness	4.42	Very Great Extent	4.33	Very Great Extent	4.38	Very Great Extent
Category Mean	4.42	Very Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.54	Very Great Extent

Table 6 shows the mean distribution of the IT experts' and users' assessment with respect to the developed system's compliance with ISO 25010 Software Standards in terms of Functional Suitability.

IT experts rated all the items with a mean rating of 4.42 and system users with a mean of 4.67, resulting to 4.54 category mean. It shows the system's compliance to a "Very Great Extent," which means that the system executes and performs its functionalities as stated by the users. The set of functions on a specified task is appropriate, provides the right and agreed results, works as per intended application, provides output that conforms to the base requirements, generates output that is the same as the expected output, and serves its purpose well.

This implies that the developed system complied with all the functionality standards of ISO 25010:2015.

B. Extent of Compliance with ISO 25010:2015 in Terms of Performance Efficiency

Table 7. The System's Compliance on Performance Efficiency as Assessed by the IT Experts and Users

Performance Efficiency	IT Experts		User		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Time behaviour	4.42	Very Great Extent	5.00	Very Great Extent	4.71	Very Great Extent
Resource utilization	4.42	Very Great Extent	5.00	Very Great Extent	4.71	Very Great Extent
Capacity	4.00	Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.33	Very Great Extent
Category Mean	4.28	Very Great Extent	4.89	Very Great Extent	4.58	Very Great Extent

Table 7 shows the mean distribution of the IT experts' and users' assessments with respect to the developed system's compliance with ISO 25010 Software Standards in terms of System Efficiency

IT experts rated all the items with a mean rating of 4.28 and system users with a mean of 4.89, resulting to 4.48 category mean. It shows that the system's compliance to

a “Very Great Extent,” which means that the system is efficient in executing the different tasks as expected by the users. The system produces desired outputs with optimum time.

This implies that in terms of time behavior, resource utilization, and capacity, the system met the particular standard.

C. Extent of Compliance with ISO 25010:2015 in Terms of Usability

Table 8. The System’s Compliance on Usability as Assessed by the IT Experts and Users

Usability	IT Experts		User		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Appropriateness recognizability	4.42	Very Great Extent	5.00	Very Great Extent	4.71	Very Great Extent
Learnability	4.42	Very Great Extent	5.00	Very Great Extent	4.71	Very Great Extent
Operability	4.00	Great Extent	5.00	Very Great Extent	4.50	Great Extent
User error protection	3.71	Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.19	Great Extent
User interface aesthetics	3.42	Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.04	VGreat Extent
Accessibility	4.14	Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.40	Very Great Extent
Category Mean	4.02	Great Extent	4.83	Very Great Extent	4.42	Very Great Extent

Table 8 shows the mean distribution of the IT experts’ and users’ assessments with respect to the developed system’s compliance with ISO 25010 Software Standards in terms of System Usability

IT experts rated all the items with a mean rating of 4.02 and system users with a mean of 4.83, resulting to 4.42 category mean. It shows that the system’s compliance to a “Very Great Extent.”

This implies that the system can be used to achieve objectives with efficiency, effectiveness, and satisfaction in a quantified context of use.

D. Extent of Compliance with ISO 25010:2015 in Terms of Reliability

Table 9. The System’s Compliance on Reliability as Assessed by the IT Experts and Users

Reliability	IT Experts		User		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Maturity	4.14	Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.40	Very Great Extent
Availability	4.28	Very Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.47	Very Great Extent
Fault tolerance	4.14	Great Extent	4.00	Very Great Extent	4.07	Great Extent

Recoverability	4.14	Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.40	Very Great Extent
Category Mean	4.17	Great Extent	4.50	Very Great Extent	4.33	Very Great Extent

Table 9 shows the mean distribution of the IT experts' and users' assessments with respect to the developed system's compliance with ISO 25010 Software Standards in terms of System Reliability.

IT experts rated all the items with a mean rating of 4.17 and system users with a mean of 4.50, resulting to 4.33 category mean. It shows that the system's compliance to a "Very Great Extent." This implies that the developed system performs its intended functions and operations based on maturity, availability, fault tolerance and recoverability.

E. Extent of Compliance with ISO 25010:2015 in Terms of Portability

Table 10. The System's Compliance on Portability as Assessed by the IT Experts and Users

Portability	IT Experts		User		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Adaptability	4.42	Very Great Extent	5.00	Very Great Extent	4.71	Very Great Extent
Installability	4.00	Great Extent	5.00	Very Great Extent	4.50	Very Great Extent
Replaceability	4.28	Very Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.47	Very Great Extent
Category Mean	4.23	Very Great Extent	4.89	Very Great Extent	4.56	Very Great Extent

Table 10 shows the mean distribution of the IT experts' and users' assessments with respect to the developed system's compliance with ISO 25010 Software Standards in terms of System Portability.

IT experts rated all the items with a mean rating of 4.23 and system users with a mean of 4.89, resulting to 4.56 category mean. It shows that the system's compliance to a "Very Great Extent." This implies that the developed system can adapt to different hardware and software environments. The system is easy to install, can be transferred from one computer to another, and can be easily integrated into another environment with consistent functional correctness.

The result further implies that the system is in compliance with the ISO 25010 Quality Software Standards in terms of System Portability.

F. Extent of Compliance with ISO 25010:2015 in Terms of Maintainability

Table 11. The System's Compliance on Maintainability as Assessed by the IT Experts and Users

Maintainability	IT Experts		User		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Modularity	4.28	Very Great Extent	4.33	Very Great Extent	4.30	Very Great Extent
Reusability	4.28	Very Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.47	Very Great Extent
Analyzability	4.42	Very Great Extent	4.33	Very Great Extent	4.38	Very Great Extent
Modifiability	4.28	Very Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.47	Very Great Extent
Testability	4.00	Great Extent	5.00	Very Great Extent	4.50	Very Great Extent
Category Mean	4.25	Very Great Extent	4.60	Very Great Extent	4.42	Very Great Extent

Table 11 shows the mean distribution of the IT experts' and users' assessments with respect to the developed system's compliance with ISO 25010 Software Standards in terms of System Maintainability.

IT experts rated all the items with a mean rating of 4.25 and system users with a mean of 4.60, resulting to 4.42 category mean. It shows that the system's compliance with a "Very Great Extent."

The result implies that the system can function if changes are made and is in compliance with the ISO 25010 Quality Software Standards in terms system maintainability.

G. Extent of Compliance with ISO 25010:2015 in Terms of Security

Table 12. The System's Compliance on Security as Assessed by the IT Experts and Users

Security	IT Experts		User		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Confidentiality	4.51	Moderate Extent	5.00	Very Great Extent	4.78	Very Great Extent
Integrity	4.28	Very Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.47	Very Great Extent
Non-repudiation	4.42	Very Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.54	Very Great Extent
Accountability	4.28	Very Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.47	Very Great Extent
Authenticity	4.14	Great Extent	5.00	Very Great Extent	4.57	Very Great Extent
Category Mean	4.34	Very Great Extent	4.80	Very Great Extent	4.57	Very Great Extent

Table 12 shows the mean distribution of the IT experts' and users' assessments with respect to the developed system's compliance with System Security of ISO 25010 Software Standards.

The IT experts rated all the items with a mean rating of 4.34 while the system users have rated with a mean of 4.80, resulting to 4.57 category mean. It shows that the system's compliance to a "Very Great Extent."

This implies that the developed system performed its function in a secure environment. The system is protected against unauthorized access; password is encrypted; user automatically logs off after a predefined period of inactivity; and audit log is present to trace user's activity in the system.

The result implies that the system is compliant with the ISO 25010 Quality Software Standards on system security.

H. Extent of Compliance with ISO 25010:2015 in Terms of Compatibility

Table 13. The System's Compliance on Compatibility as Assessed by the IT Experts and Users

	IT Experts		User		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Compatibility						
Co-existence	4.14	Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.40	Very Great Extent
Interoperability	4.14	Great Extent	5.00	Very Great Extent	4.57	Very Great Extent
Category Mean	4.14	Great Extent	4.83	Very Great Extent	4.48	Very Great Extent

Table 13 shows the mean distribution of the IT experts' and users' assessments with respect to the developed system's compliance with ISO 25010 Software Standards in terms of System Compatibility.

In the table above, the IT Experts rated the indicators with a mean rating of 4.14 and system users with a mean of 4.83, resulting to 4.48 as category mean. It shows that the system's compliance to a "Very Great Extent," which suggests that there is interoperability of the developed system. The system executes its functionalities efficiently while sharing the environment and resources with other systems configurations and specifications.

The result also implies that the system is compliant with the ISO 25010 Quality Software Standards on system compatibility.

Table 14. The System's Overall Compliance to ISO 25010:2015

Attributes	IT Experts		User		Overall	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Functionality Suitability	4.42	Very Great Extent	4.67	Very Great Extent	4.54	Very Great Extent
Performance Efficiency	4.28	Very Great Extent	4.89	Very Great Extent	4.58	Very Great Extent
Usability	4.02	Great Extent	4.83	Very Great Extent	4.42	Very Great Extent
Reliability	4.17	Great Extent	4.50	Very Great Extent	4.33	Very Great Extent

Portability	4.23	Very Great Extent	4.89	Very Great Extent	4.56	Very Great Extent
Maintainability	4.25	Very Great Extent	4.60	Very Great Extent	4.42	Very Great Extent
Security	4.34	Very Great Extent	4.80	Very Great Extent	4.57	Very Great Extent
Compatibility	4.14	Great Extent	4.83	Very Great Extent	4.48	Very Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.23	Very Great Extent	4.75	Very Great Extent	4.48	Very Great Extent

The data presented in Table 14 reflects the overall compliance of the system to the ISO 25010:2015 software quality standards, as evaluated by both IT experts and end-users. The evaluation covers key attributes of software quality, namely functionality suitability, performance efficiency, usability, reliability, portability, maintainability, security, and compatibility.

Overall, both IT experts and users assessed the system as compliant to a *very great extent*, with an overall mean rating of 4.23 from IT experts and 4.75 from users, resulting in a combined overall mean of 4.48. This indicates a strong consensus on the high quality of the system across different stakeholder perspectives. Among the attributes, *performance efficiency* and *portability* received particularly high ratings from users (both at 4.89), reflecting a strong user satisfaction with how the system performs under expected workloads and its adaptability across various environments. The IT experts also rated these attributes highly, though slightly lower, with scores of 4.28 and 4.23, respectively.

Functionality suitability and *security* were also rated very highly by both groups, suggesting that the system effectively meets its intended purposes and incorporates robust protection mechanisms against threats. Notably, *usability*, *reliability*, and *compatibility* were rated slightly lower by IT experts (ranging from 4.02 to 4.17), indicating areas where technical reviewers might see room for improvement in terms of system interface, error tolerance, and interoperability. However, users rated these same attributes significantly higher (from 4.50 to 4.83), pointing to a generally favorable user experience.

The consistency of high ratings across all attributes and by both evaluators underscores the system's strong alignment with ISO 25010:2015 standards. The minor discrepancies between IT expert and user ratings suggest potential areas for technical refinement while maintaining user satisfaction. Overall, the system demonstrates a high level of software quality and effectiveness in meeting the needs of its users and stakeholders.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the developed Barangay ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) system serves as an effective tool for Local Government Units (LGUs), aiding Barangay Officials in efficiently performing their management functions and decision making. The system provides essential information enabling informed decision-making to enhance operational efficiency and support long-term sustainability. Furthermore, the developed system complies with the ISO 25010 Software Quality Standards, ensuring its functionality suitability, performance efficiency, usability, reliability, portability, maintainability, security, and compatibility assessed as compliant to a *very great extent*, with an overall mean rating of 4.23 from IT experts and 4.75 from users, resulting in a combined overall mean of 4.48.

References

- Abdirahman, H. (n.d.) Decision support system models. <https://www.scribd.com/presentation/208748149/Decision-Support-System-Models>.
- Alegre, M. A., (2020). "Data-Driven Governance: The Key to Informed Decision-Making in Local Government Units." *International Journal of Public Administration*.
- Alampay, E., (2017). "The State of E-Governance in the Philippines: Findings from a Nationwide Baseline Study." *Asian Institute of Journalism and Communication*.
- Castro, E. T., & Romano, N. P. (2022, June). Mining on Senior Citizens Data: Empirical Evidence in the Philippines Locale" Basis for Social Services Improvement and Decision Making". In *2022 IEEE International Conference on Automatic Control and Intelligent Systems (I2CACIS)* (pp. 197-202). IEEE.
- Carpio, C.O (2020) "Barangay management system," *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications (IJMRAP)*, Volume 3, Issue 2, pp. 26-32, 2020.
- Cerna, M. A. D. (2023, May). Development and Implementation of an Office Automation System for Barangay Local Government Units. In *2023 4th International Conference for Emerging Technology (INCET)* (pp. 1-9). IEEE.
- Cruz, L. A. D., Balilia, C. J., Abana, E., Pagulayan, L., Mebaña, J. E., Datul, D. J., & Acoba, J. A. (2023, December). Enhanced Barangay Information Management System with Residency Certificate Issuance. In *2023 IEEE 8th International Conference on Recent Advances and Innovations in Engineering (ICRAIE)* (pp. 1-7). IEEE.
- Delima, R., Santosa, H. B., & Purwadi, J. (2017). Development of Dutatani Website Using Rapid Application Development. *International Journal of Information Technology and Electrical Engineering*, 1(2), 36-44. <https://journal.ugm.ac.id/ijitee/article/view/28362/17267>
- Elgendy, N., Elragal, A., & Päivärinta, T. (2022). DECAS: a modern data-driven decision theory for big data and analytics. *Journal of Decision Systems*, 31(4), 337-373.
- França, J. M., & Soares, M. S. (2015). SOAQM: Quality model for SOA applications based on ISO 25010. In *ICEIS* (2) (pp. 60-70). <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/0330/e104d36445a8fc151d915462bd9137098a4c.pdf>

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 33 of 38

- Gogoll, J., Zuber, N., Kacianka, S., Greger, T., Pretschner, A., & Nida-Rümelin, J. (2021). Ethics in the software development process: from codes of conduct to ethical deliberation. *Philosophy & Technology*, 1-24.
- Gonzalez, J., (2019). "The Role of Enterprise Resource Planning Systems in Strengthening Financial Management Practices in Local Government Units: A Case Study of Selected Municipalities in the Philippines." *Journal of Finance and Economics*.
- Garefalakis, A., Mantalis, G., Vourgourakis, E., Spinthropoulos, K., & Lemonakis, C. (2016). Healthcare firms and the ERP systems. *Journal of Engineering Science & Technology Review*, 9(1).
https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Alexandros_Garefalakis/publication/309118459_Healthcare_Firms_and_the_ERP_Systems/links/5803135c08ae23fd1b673d4d/Healthcare-Firms-and-the-ERP-Systems.pdf
- Himo, A.J., Medina, A.G., Santos, J. M., Servito, J.G., Alegado, R.T. (2022) "Community request queue management system for local government unit of Cabanatuan City," *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering*, 11(6), November - December 2022, 285 – 293.
- Kokate, S. (2014). E-College: An ERP for educational Institute. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Shrikant_Kokate2/publication/283321433_ECollege_An_ERP_for_Educational_Institute/links/5633438908ae5848780aaea3/E-College-An-ERP-for-Educational-Institute.pdf
- Kravchenko, I. (2018). Is there any difference between MIS and ERP.
<https://diceus.com/difference-between-mis-and-erp/>
- Mendoza, R., (2018). "E-Governance in the Philippines: The State of Local E-Governance Websites." *Asian Institute of Journalism and Communication*.
- National ICT Confederation of the Philippines. (2018). The Role of ICT in Barangay Governance. Retrieved from <http://nicto.org.ph/publications/articles/the-role-of-ict-in-barangay-governance/>
- Smith, A. (2021). The Role of Information and Communication Technology in Modern Society. *Tech Insights Magazine*.
- Tacuban, T. N. (2016). Barangay Decision Support and Mapping System. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 4(2).

Appendices

EVALUATION FORM

Empowering Barangays: Harnessing Data for Effective Decision Making through Enterprise Resource Planning Systems
 EVALUATION using ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards

Dear Respondent,

We am currently undertaking a research project which is Empowering Barangays: Harnessing Data for Effective Decision Making through Enterprise Resource Planning Systems With this, we humbly request for your support by providing the data needed below for evaluation purposes. The data will be of great help for the completion of our final project paper

Thank you very much.

Adonis V. Garces, DIT
 Milagros S. constantino, MIT
 Reynaldo A. Valdez, Baragnay Captgain

Please check the box that best represents your assessment on the extent of compliance to ISO 25010:2015 of the developed Empowering Barangays: Harnessing Data for Effective Decision Making through Enterprise Resource Planning Systems in terms of Functionality, Efficiency, Usability, Reliability, Portability, and Maintainability and using the following scale:

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|----------------------------------|
| 5 - Compliant to a very great extent | 4 - Compliant to a great extent |
| 3 - Compliant to a moderate extent | 2 - Compliant to a little extent |
| 1 - Compliant to a very little extent | |

ISO 25010 Software Quality Standards	5	4	3	2	1
A. Functional Suitability					
Functional completeness It covers all the specified tasks and user objectives					
Functional correctness It provides the correct results with the needed degree of precision					
Functional appropriateness Facilitate the accomplishment of specified tasks and objectives					
B. Performance Efficiency					
Time behaviour Meet the requirements in the response and processing time when performing its functions					
Resource utilization Meet the requirements in the amounts and types of resources used when performing its functions					
Capacity Meet the requirements in the maximum limits					
C. Compatibility	5	4	3	2	1
Co-existence					

Can perform its required functions efficiently while sharing a common environment and resources					
Interoperability Components can exchange information and use the information that has been exchanged					
D. Usability	5	4	3	2	1
Appropriateness recognizability It is appropriate to the needs of the users.					
Learnability Can be used to achieve specified goals of learning with effectiveness, efficiency, freedom from risk and satisfaction in a specified context of use					
Operability It is easy to operate and control					
User error protection Protects users against making errors					
User interface aesthetics Its interface enables pleasing and satisfying interaction for the user					
Accessibility Can be used to a widest range of characteristics and capabilities to achieve a specified goal in a specified context of use					
E. Reliability	5	4	3	2	1
Maturity Meets the need for reliability under normal operation					
Availability It is operational and accessible when required for use					
Fault tolerance It operates as intended despite the presence of hardware or software faults					
Recoverability Can recover the data directly affected and re-establish the desired state.					
F. Security	5	4	3	2	1
Confidentiality Ensures that the data are accessible only to those authorized to have access					
Integrity Prevents unauthorized access to, or modification of programs or data					
Non-repudiation Can be proven to have taken place, so that it cannot be repudiated later					
Accountability Actions of an entity can be traced uniquely to the entity					
Authenticity The identity of a subject can be proved to be the one claimed					
G. Maintainability	5	4	3	2	1
Modularity Composed of discrete components such that a change to one component has minimal impact on other components					
Reusability Assets can be used in more than one system, or in building other assets					
Analysability It is possible to assess the impact of an intended change to one or more of its parts, or to diagnose deficiencies or cause of failures					
Modifiability Can be effectively and efficiently modified without introducing defects or degrading existing product quality					
Testability Test Criteria can be established and can be performed to determine whether those criteria have been met					

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 36 of 38

H.Portability	5	4	3	2	1
Adaptability Effectively and efficiently be adapted for evolving hardware, software or other usage environments					
Installability Can be successfully installed and/or uninstalled in a specified environment					
Replaceability Can replace another specified software product for the same purpose in the same environment.					

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 37 of 38

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-070, Rev 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	1 of 1

ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

This certifies that the following protocol and related documents have been approved, monitored, and granted clearance by SMUREB.

SMUREB Code: 2024 0679
Research Proponent/s: ADONIS V. GARCES, DIT
 MILAGROS S. CONSTANTINO, MIT
 REYNALDO A. VALDEZ
Title: Empowering Barangays: Harnessing Data for Effective Decision Making through Enterprise Resource Planning Systems
Protocol Version No.: 1
Version Date: July 10, 2024
ICF Version No.: 1
Version Date: July 10, 2024
Type of Review: Expedited

The research proponent has submitted the final report form and has complied with all the requirements of the Research Ethics Board.

Issued and signed on May 6, 2025.

JASON ARNOLD L. MASLANG
 Chair, SMUREB

*Inspired by Mission,
 Driven by Excellence*

Second Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Building
 SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos
 Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines
 www.smu.edu.ph / reb@smu.edu.ph
 078-321-2221 / 09177053041

*Inspired by Mission,
 Driven by Excellence*

Second Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Building
 SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, District IV
 Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines
 www.smu.edu.ph / ddacles@smu.edu.ph
 (078) 392-8150

Document Code	EOMS-URC-FO-050, Rev. 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	Page 38 of 38

Document Code	SOMS-RBO-FO-064, Rev 00
Effectivity Date	2024/12/08
Page/s	1 of 1

DECISION LETTER ON FINAL REPORT

May 6, 2025

ADONIS V. GARCES
 Faculty Research
 This University

RE: *Empowering Barangays: Harnessing Data for Effective Decision Making through Enterprise Resource Planning Systems*

SMUREB code: 2024 0679

Subject: Review of Final Report

Dear Mr. Garces,

Your submitted final report on April 28, 2025 has undergone Expedited review, which generated the following:

Findings

1. Findings are aligned with the approved research objectives
2. Study results are disseminated during an institutional research forum.

Decision

- Accepted
- Require resubmission with correction

Recommendation

Claim ethics clearance certificate from the University Research Ethics Office..

Very truly yours,

DR. KENNETH L. MASLANG
 Primary Reviewer

JASON ARNOLD L. MASLANG
 Chair, SMUREB

*Inspired by Mission,
 Driven by Excellence*

Second Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Building
 SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos
 Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines
 www.smu.edu.ph / reb@smu.edu.ph
 078-321-2221 / 09177053041